

Acute Neonatal Appendicitis: A Report of a Complicated Case in the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit

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ABSTRACT

ARTICLE DETAILS

Introduction: Neonatal appendicitis is an extremely rare and potentially serious condition, whose nonspecific clinical presentation hinders timely diagnosis and is associated with a high rate of intestinal perforation. Clinical overlap with common neonatal conditions, such as sepsis or necrotizing enterocolitis, poses a significant diagnostic challenge.

Case Presentation: We describe the case of a full-term newborn with intrauterine growth restriction who was admitted with suspected early neonatal sepsis. During her course, she presented with progressive abdominal distension, episodes of apnea, hemodynamic instability, and a marked elevation in inflammatory markers, with a blood culture positive for *Escherichia coli*. She subsequently developed bilious vomiting and increased abdominal distension, leading to an exploratory laparotomy, which identified a hyperemic retrocecal appendix with perforation in the middle third, confirming acute perforated appendicitis. An appendectomy was performed, and targeted antimicrobial therapy and intensive supportive care were initiated, with a favorable clinical outcome.

Conclusion: Neonatal appendicitis should be considered in the differential diagnosis of acute abdomen in the newborn, especially in the presence of progressive abdominal distension, bilious vomiting, or clinical deterioration without apparent cause. Early suspicion, timely surgical intervention, and comprehensive multidisciplinary management are critical for improving the prognosis.

KEYWORDS: neonatal appendicitis; acute abdomen; intestinal perforation; neonatal sepsis; neonatal surgery.

Published On:
28 April

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

In the pediatric population, one of the most common causes of surgical abdomen is acute appendicitis, which is also one of the leading surgical emergencies from school age through adolescence. Its incidence varies by age, peaking between 10 and 14 years, with an estimated frequency of 4 per 1,000 children under 14 years of age undergoing surgery annually in countries such as the United States¹. In Mexico, it has been reported that between 1% and 8% of pediatric patients presenting to the emergency department with abdominal pain are diagnosed with appendicitis, with the condition being more common in boys and school-aged children².

The pathophysiology of this condition is based on obstruction of the appendicular lumen, whether due to lymphoid hyperplasia, fecaliths, or foreign bodies, which triggers a progressive inflammatory process with a risk of ischemia, necrosis, and perforation. The classic clinical presentation includes abdominal pain migrating to the right iliac fossa, fever, nausea, and vomiting; however, in children under five years of age, the presentation may be atypical, which increases the risk of delayed diagnosis and complications such as peritonitis or intra-abdominal abscesses³.

Diagnosis is based on clinical evaluation, scales such as the Alvarado and PAS scores, and imaging studies, with abdominal ultrasound being the initial method of choice due to its safety and efficacy. In cases that are difficult to interpret,

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computed tomography or magnetic resonance imaging may be useful. The standard treatment remains open or laparoscopic appendectomy,

Image 2. Stage IV appendectomy.
SOURCE: obtained from the clinical record for academic purposes.

although conservative management with antibiotics has been explored in selected cases of uncomplicated appendicitis. The incorporation of emerging biomarkers, such as C-reactive protein and procalcitonin, as well as an individualized therapeutic approach, has been shown to improve prognosis and reduce complications in the pediatric population¹.

In contrast, appendicitis in the neonatal period is a unique clinical entity, with an estimated incidence of between 0.04% and 0.2% of all cases of childhood appendicitis⁴. Its rarity, coupled with nonspecific clinical presentation—such as abdominal distension, vomiting, fever, or irritability—and frequent confusion with other conditions such as necrotizing enterocolitis, contributes to delayed diagnosis and a high rate of perforation, which can reach up to 80%^{5,6}. Factors such as immunological immaturity, the small size of

the abdominal cavity, and the rapid spread of infection worsen the prognosis^{7,8}. Additionally, associations have been described with other neonatal conditions such as prematurity, intrauterine sepsis, incarcerated hernias, and inflammatory conditions, such as necrotizing enterocolitis or Hirschsprung's disease^{9,4}.

The importance of managing neonatal appendicitis lies in its high morbidity and mortality rates and in the need to maintain a high clinical suspicion of the condition in any case of acute abdomen in the newborn. Despite advances in diagnosis, most cases are identified intraoperatively, and delays in timely surgical treatment can have fatal consequences. Historically, neonatal mortality from appendicitis was close to 100%, although it is currently estimated to be between 20% and 30% thanks to increased clinical awareness and improvements in therapeutic management^{10,11}. This reality, compared with the low mortality rate observed in older children—which ranges from 0.1% to 1%—highlights the lack of diagnostic strategies in the neonate³.

Therefore, studying appendicitis in its various forms—from the typical presentation in school-aged children to the atypical

and life-threatening form in newborns—is essential for improving diagnostic and treatment algorithms, reducing complications, and improving clinical outcomes. Understanding its clinical, epidemiological, and pathophysiological characteristics allows not only for better individualized care but also for the development of more effective health policies in vulnerable pediatric settings.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 38-week-old female newborn with a CAPURRO score and asymmetric intrauterine growth restriction (2330 g) was admitted for suspected early neonatal sepsis (history of urinary tract infection during pregnancy and irregular prenatal care). Treatment was initiated with ampicillin and amikacin. During the first two days, she presented with progressive abdominal distension without respiratory compromise.

Around the third day of life, she developed two episodes of apnea with hemodynamic compromise, requiring intubation and sedation in the neonatal intensive care unit. She developed bradycardia and hypotension, so support was initiated with dobutamine and subsequently norepinephrine. The initial blood culture was positive for *Escherichia coli*, and the antimicrobial regimen was adjusted to include cefotaxime.

Subsequently, septic shock was documented with the following biomarkers:

- CRP 121.6 mg/L
- Procalcitonin 117.6 ng/mL
- WBC $5.3 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$
- Platelets $110 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$
- Blood gas: pH 7.44, PCO₂ 23.4 mmHg, HCO₃ 16.2 mmol/L, lactate 2.5 mmol/L

Image 1. X-ray suggestive of intestinal obstruction. **SOURCE:** obtained from the clinical record for academic purposes.

Treatment was escalated to meropenem.

Around the seventh day, she presented with bile output via an orogastric tube and increased abdominal distension. A new X-ray was performed (Image 1),

which suggested meconium ileus, and an exploratory laparotomy was performed, revealing distended loops with fibrinopurulent membranes and a hyperemic retrocecal appendix with perforation in the middle third. An appendectomy was performed, confirming stage IV perforated acute appendicitis (Image 2).

Postoperatively, metronidazole was added, and total parenteral nutrition was initiated.

In the following days, the patient showed progressive improvement, with a sustained decrease in inflammatory markers: around day 15, CRP was 29.3 mg/L, PCT 0.43 ng/mL, WBC $28.6 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$, and platelets $458 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$; by day 18, CRP was 13.38 mg/L, PCT 0.14 ng/mL, hemoglobin 11.8 g/dL, and platelets $129 \times 10^3/\text{mm}^3$.

Subsequent cultures identified:

- *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in a central blood culture
- *K. pneumoniae* and yeast in a peripheral blood culture
- *Candida* sp. in a urine culture

These were associated with nosocomial infections; therefore, the patient received levofloxacin and amphotericin B for seven days, with an adequate response.

By the end of the fourth week of life, the infant was stable, afebrile, tolerating oral intake, without ventilatory or hemodynamic support, and with normalized inflammatory markers. She was discharged weighing 2575 g, with instructions for feeding on demand, medical treatment, and follow-up by the neonatology team.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Informed consent was obtained from the mother for the treatment and performance of the procedures described in this case. Case information was handled confidentially and anonymized. This study was reviewed and evaluated by the Research Committee CI-2025-055-HGC and the Research Ethics Committee CEI-2025-055-HGC of the General Hospital of Cancún.

DISCUSSION

Neonatal appendicitis is a unique condition within the spectrum of acute abdomen, with a reported incidence of between 0.04% and 0.2% of childhood appendicitis cases, which explains the limited clinical experience and associated diagnostic difficulty^{4,5}. Its clinical presentation is often nonspecific and easily attributed to more common conditions in the neonatal period, such as necrotizing enterocolitis, spontaneous intestinal perforation, or neonatal sepsis, which contributes to delayed diagnosis and a high rate of perforation, which can exceed 80%^{6,12}.

The case presented reflects this diagnostic complexity, as the patient initially presented with progressive abdominal distension in the context of early neonatal sepsis caused by *Escherichia coli*, which delayed suspicion of an underlying surgical condition.

Unlike appendicitis in older children, whose pathophysiology is primarily associated with luminal obstruction due to lymphoid hyperplasia or fecaliths¹, it has been proposed that appendicular inflammation in neonates is secondary to hypoxia, mesenteric vascular compromise, systemic sepsis, or intestinal inflammatory processes^{7,13}. In this case, the presence of septic shock, leukopenia, thrombocytopenia, and a marked elevation of inflammatory biomarkers suggests a pathophysiological environment that may have contributed to the rapid progression toward perforation.

The initial symptoms—abdominal distension, food intolerance, and hemodynamic deterioration—are consistent with those described in multiple series and case reports^{14,15}. The onset of bilious vomiting and the radiographic finding suggestive of meconium ileus prompted surgical intervention. As in most published cases, the definitive diagnosis was established intraoperatively, revealing a hyperemic retrocecal appendix with perforation and fibrinopurulent membranes—findings characteristic of perforated appendicitis in neonates^{16,17}.

Timely surgical management, along with intensive care and targeted antimicrobial therapy, was crucial for the patient's favorable outcome. The subsequent identification of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Candida* sp. in cultures is consistent with reports in critically ill neonates, who are more

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susceptible to nosocomial infections and bacterial translocation, particularly in the context of intestinal perforation and parenteral nutrition^{18,8}.

The case highlights the need to maintain diagnostic suspicion in any newborn with progressive abdominal distension, bilious vomiting, or unexplained clinical deterioration, even when a plausible alternative diagnosis such as neonatal sepsis exists. The coexistence of systemic infection and surgical pathology can mask abdominal progression, delaying intervention^{9,11}.

Finally, the patient's favorable outcome reflects progress in the comprehensive management of critically ill neonates, including early surgery, personalized hemodynamic support, and targeted antibiotic therapy. This case emphasizes the need for more sensitive diagnostic strategies and greater clinical awareness to reduce morbidity and mortality¹⁰.

CONCLUSIONS

Neonatal appendicitis, although extremely rare, constitutes a serious cause of acute abdomen with high morbidity and mortality due to its nonspecific clinical presentation and typically delayed diagnosis. The coexistence of neonatal sepsis and abdominal distress can mask an underlying surgical process, delaying its identification.

The presence of progressive abdominal distension, bilious vomiting, or hemodynamic instability in a newborn should prompt a comprehensive evaluation that includes the possibility of appendicitis. Early surgical intervention, adequate hemodynamic support, and targeted antimicrobial therapy are essential for improving outcomes.

This case underscores the importance of developing more sensitive diagnostic strategies and maintaining close monitoring for atypical abdominal signs in neonates.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I am deeply grateful to the Faculty of Medicine at the Autonomous University of Yucatán for its commitment to academic training and the promotion of clinical research, which were fundamental to the development of this study.

Likewise, I express my gratitude to the "Jesús Kumate Rodríguez" General Hospital of Cancún, whose multidisciplinary team provided the necessary conditions for patient care and the rigorous collection of clinical information that made this case study possible.

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